

Orographic and land-sea contrast effects in convection-permitting simulations of extreme sub-daily precipitation

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This readme file contains a description of the data and codes used in the article “Orographic and land-sea contrast effects in convection-permitting simulations of extreme sub-daily precipitation”.

A1_computation_lmoments.m is the routine used to compute the L-moments of the series. This code takes advantage of the function lmoments.m.

The input files needed to run the code are:

- sample_DATASET_I2-RED_rainfall.xlsx is an Excel file containing the time series of the annual maxima derived by rain gauge observations, structured as follows:
 - row 1 – station ID;
 - row 2 – year;
 - rows 3 to 7 – annual maximum rainfall depths computed for the 1, 3, 6, 12 and 24 h durations, expressed in mm.
- sample_DATASET_I2-RED_coord.csv is a csv file containing the station coordinates, structured as follows:
 - row 1 – station ID;
 - rows 2 to 3 – station coordinates (WGS 84 UTM 32 N - EPSG 32632 in our case).

sample_DATASET_I2-RED_coord.csv and sample_DATASET_I2-RED_rainfall.xlsx contains the data of 3 time series located in Piedmont (NW Italy), for testing purposes. The same code can be executed by using as input VHR-PRO_IT data. Also in this case, sample_DATASET_VHR-PRO-IT_rainfall.xlsx is made available for testing purposes.

L-moments can be computed by using only the data of the station itself (single-station approach) or by adding the data of the closest, or 2 closest, rain gauges (regionalization approach).

In rows 10-11 the user can identify the time period to be used in the analysis.

A2_computation_quantiles.m is the routine used to compute the rainfall quantiles by using a GEV distribution.

In row 5, the number of stations needed to compute the quantiles should be stated. Rows 7 to 20 allow user to import data computed by running A1_computation_lmoments.m separately on the two datasets.

res_ID_heterogeneous.xlsx (mentioned in row 24) is an Excel file that contains the station ID removed after the application of the Hosking and Wallis homogeneity test.